

Syntheses and properties of organotin(IV) dialkyl phosphites

Padam Nabh Nagar

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

E-mail : rkbohra@satyam.net.in

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The reaction of organotin chlorides with sodium dialkyl phosphites in solvent benzene/ether yielded organotin dialkyl phosphites. The identical products were also obtained when organotin chlorides were initially complexed with dialkyl phosphonates and then heated with triethylamine. These compounds have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements, IR and NMR (^1H , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn) spectral data.

In continuation of our earlier investigations on the dialkyl phosphonate¹⁻³ and dialkylthiophosphonate (open chain and cyclic)³ derivatives of tin(IV)^{2,3} and arsenic(III)¹. We report here the reactions of sodium dialkyl phosphites or dialkyl phosphonate anions with organotin chlorides.

Results and discussion

In the present investigations the sodium dialkyl phosphites have been prepared *in situ* (as these cannot be stored for a long time) and caused to react with tri- and diorganotin chlorides in nitrogen atmosphere which yield organotin(IV) dialkyl phosphites. The reaction proceeds to completion at ambient temperatures in solvent ether while in benzene it requires refluxing (10–12 h).

[where, R = Me, Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ; R' = Me, Et, Ph]

When organotin chlorides were initially complexed with dialkyl phosphonates and then heated with triethylamine in benzene then the separation of triethylamine hydrochloride is smooth and organotin dialkyl phosphites were obtained.

[where, R = Et, Prⁱ; R' = Et, Buⁿ]

[where R = Me, Et; R' = Me, Et]

IR spectra :

A comparison of the IR spectra of the organotin dialkyl phosphites with those of the starting materials shows the following characteristic changes. (i) disappearance of $\nu_{\text{P-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Sn-Cl}}$ bands which are present at 2425 ± 5 and $350 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the reactants, (ii) disappearance of $\nu_{\text{P=O}}$ bands $1270\text{--}1190 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, (iii) appearance of a new band at $770\text{--}640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Sn-O-P) and (iv) (P)-O-(C) absorption bands are retained in the products and are present in the same range as in dialkyl phosphonates ($1168\text{--}910 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The position of $\nu_{\text{Sn-O-P}}$ absorption band was assigned on the basis, that there is no absorption band in the region ($600\text{--}750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in free dialkyl phosphonates as well as in organotin chlorides. The organotin dialkyl phosphites on exposure to atmospheric oxygen show the appearance of a broad and diffuse absorption band in the phosphoryl ($\nu_{\text{P=O}}$) region ($1170\text{--}1210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating sensitivity of these compounds towards oxygen. The shifting of phosphoryl ($\nu_{\text{P=O}}$) absorption band at lower frequencies in the oxidized product indicates the presence of intermolecular coordination from phosphoryl (P=O) group to tin atom (Table 1).

NMR (^1H , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn) spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectra of the organotin dialkyl phosphites show characteristic resonances of the corresponding alkyl groups present on tin atom and alkoxy groups present on phosphorus atom (Table 2). The P-H NMR signal present at δ 6.8 ppm in $(\text{RO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ was expectedly absent. The CHOP and CH_2OP NMR signals appear as complex multiplets due to the coupling with the phosphorus atom. In case of $\text{Me}_3\text{SnOP}(\text{OEt})_2$ the J $^{119}\text{Sn-C-H}$ has been found to be 54 cps and in $\text{Me}_3\text{SnOP}(\text{OPr}^n)_2$ J $^{119}\text{Sn-C-H} = 63.67$

Table 1. Analytical and IR data of the organotin(IV) dialkyl phosphites

Compd. (% yield)	B.p °C (mm)	% Sn found (Calcd.)	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)			
			P-O-(C)	(P)-O-C	Sn=O=P	Sn-C
Me ₃ SnOP(OMe) ₂ (50)	130 (3.5) Sublimes	43.46 (43.52)	1030	545	775	546
Me ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂ (49)	70–72 (7.1)	38.85 (39.47)	1030	980	775	540
Et ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂ (41)	55 (0.25)	34.58 (34.64)	1110	980	675	510
Et ₃ SnOP(OBu ⁿ) ₂ (49)	75–78 (0.15)	29.54 (29.76)	1130	900	670	520
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂ (25)	80–85 (0.15)	29.83 (30.85)	1070	920	670	510
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁿ) ₂ (46)	58–60 (0.25)	27.24 (28.76)	1050	900	810, 710	540
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁱ) ₂ (66)	75–80 (0.15)	27.27 (28.76)	1060	980	670	520, 440
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂ (46)	98 (0.5)	27.50 (27.81)	1060	960–1030	670	540
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁿ) ₂ (77)	100 (0.2)	26.28 (26.10)	1060	990	690, 675	530
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁱ) ₂ (56)	95–98 (0.25)	26.02 (26.10)	1090–1040	940	670	550, 540
Me ₂ Sn[OP(OEt) ₂] ₂ (37)	85–90 (0.5)	28.09 (28.33)	1030–910	980	770	540
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OEt) ₂] ₂ (90)	–	25.87 (26.33)	1130–900	820	670	550, 490
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁿ) ₂] ₂ (66)	–	23.31 (23.42)	100–920	810	670	520
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂	90–95 (0.3)	23.15 (23.42)	1080–910	810	690	550, 495
Ph ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁿ) ₂] ₂	Decomp.	19.38 (19.69)	1100–940	840	680	730, 690, 680 (Sn-Ph)
Ph ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂	Decomp.	19.36 (19.69)	1080–920	880	640	735, 690, 680

Mol. wt. : *n*-Pr₃SnOP(OPrⁿ)₂, Found 405, Calcd. 412.7; *n*-Bu₃SnOP(OPrⁿ)₂, Found 450, Calcd. 454.7;
n-Bu₃SnOP(OPrⁱ)₂, Found 453.4, Calcd. 454.7; Et₃SnOP(OPrⁿ)₂, Found 500, Calcd. 506.7.

Table 2. NMR (¹H and ³¹P) spectral data for organotin(IV) dialkyl phosphites

Compd.	Chemical shifts, ¹ H ppm	³¹ P ppm	
		Sn-O-P	Sn-OP=O
Me ₃ SnOP(OMe) ₂	0.7 s (MeSn), <i>J</i> ¹¹⁹ Sn-C-H = 54 Hz, 3.4 q (OCH ₃)	141.5	–
Me ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂	0.6 s (MeSn), 0.9 and 1.1 s 1.3 t (Me), 4.1 m (CHOP)	140	8.54
Et ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂	1.1–1.58 m (Et, Me), 3.68–4.68 (CH ₂ OP)	138	1.69
Et ₃ SnOP(OBu ⁿ) ₂	0.99 q (CH ₂ Sn), 1.11 t (Me), 2.0 m (CH ₂) ₂ , 3.66 m (CH ₂ OP)	–	1.85
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂	0.67–1.77 m (Pr ⁿ , Me), 3.57–4.27 m (CH ₂ OP)	–	–
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁿ) ₂	0.67–1.33 q and d (Et, CH ₂ Sn), 3.50–4.15 sext. (CH ₂ OP)	141.6	9.69
<i>n</i> -Pr ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁱ) ₂	0.78, 1.11 d (Me, CH ₂ Sn), 1.22 d (Et), 1.55 sext. (-CH ₂ -), 3.99 m (CHOP), 4.55 m (CHOP) (two set)	139.4	8.69
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OEt) ₂	1.0 t (Me), 1.1–1.8 m (CH ₂), 3, 3.5–4.3 m (CH ₂ OP)	139.2	2.19
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁿ) ₂	1.1 t (Me), 1.4 t (-CH ₂ -), 1.7 m -(CH ₂) ₃ -, 3.6–4.2 m (CH ₂ OP)	–	–
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ SnOP(OPr ⁱ) ₂	0.86–1.67 m (Me, Bu ⁿ), 3.77–4.33 and 4.33–5.1 m (CHOP)	139.5	3.85
Me ₂ Sn[OP(OEt) ₂] ₂	0.7 s (MeSn), 0.9 and 1.1 s (<i>J</i> ¹¹⁹ Sn-C-H = 56 Hz), 1.4 t (Me), 4.2 m (CH ₂ OP)	139.56	–
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OEt) ₂] ₂	1.0–1.6 m (Me, EtSn), 3.7–4.7 m (CH ₂ OP)	–	–
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁿ) ₂] ₂	1.0–1.5 m (Me, EtSn), 1.2–1.4 q (-CH ₂ -), 3.5–4.0 m (CH ₂ OP)	–	–
Et ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂	1.0–1.5 m (Me, EtSn), 4.2 m (CHOP)	–	–
Ph ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁿ) ₂] ₂	0.7–1.1 t (Me), 1.2–1.5 q (-CH ₂ -), 3.6–4 sext. (CH ₂ OP), 1.3 m (PhSn)	–	–
Ph ₂ Sn[OP(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂	1.2 d (Me ₂ C), 4.1–4.5 m (CHOP), 1.2 m (PHSn)	–	–

cps. These values point to the tetracoordinate nature of tin atom in these compounds.

The ³¹P NMR spectra show resonance peak in the region of tricovalent phosphorus atom. In decoupled spectra,

a single resonance peak was present at 140 ± 2 ppm which supports formation of direct Sn-O-P linkage rather than Sn-P(O) linkage. On exposure to oxygen these show shifting on ^{31}P resonance peak from tricovalent region (139 ± 2 ppm) to tetravalent region (1.7–9.7 ppm) of phosphorus atom. It appears that these tend to oxidized into the corresponding organotin(IV) dialkyl phosphates (Table 2). The ^{119}Sn NMR spectral data of only one compound, $\text{Pr}_3^{\text{n}}\text{SnOP}(\text{OPr}^{\text{n}})_2$ could be obtained. A single sharp resonance peak at 137.38 ppm was present indicating tetracoordinate nature of tin atom which was also deduced from the ^{119}Sn -C-H coupling constant value in the ^1H NMR spectra.

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture and oxygen during experimental manipulations. Dialkyl phosphonates were synthesized by the reported methods⁴. Organotin chlorides were distilled before use. Tin was estimated gravimetrically as $\text{SnO}_2 \cdot \text{OCH}_2\text{O}$. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in refluxing benzene. IR spectra (4000 – 200 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrometer using CsI cells and NMR (^1H , ^{31}P and ^{119}Sn) spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{CCl}_4$) on a JEOL FX 900 spectrometer.

Methods of preparation :

Reaction between $\text{Bu}_3^{\text{n}}\text{SnCl}$ and $(\text{Pr}^{\text{n}}\text{O})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ in presence of sodium :

To a calculated quantity of sodium wire (0.43 g) in benzene (~50 ml) in the atmosphere of nitrogen was added dropwise a benzene solution of di-n-propyl phosphonate (3.52 g) slowly and the contents were refluxed for 4–6 h until a clear solution was obtained. To it was added, in N_2

atmosphere, a benzene solution (~20 ml) of tributyltin chloride (6.15 g) dropwise with stirring. Sodium chloride was precipitated. The contents were further refluxed for 4–6 h to ensure completion of the reaction. Sodium chloride (1.1 g) was filtered off and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product tributyltin(IV) dipropyl phosphites (6.9 g, 90%) was obtained as transparent liquid (Found : Sn, 26.28. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_3\text{PSn}$ calcd. for : Sn, 26.10%). The product was finally distilled at $100^\circ/0.2$ mm, yield 80% (Table 1).

Reaction between Et_3SnCl and $(\text{EtO})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{H}$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of Et_3N : To a mixture of triethyltin chloride (2.59 g) and diethyl phosphonate (1.48 g) in benzene (~40 ml), was added a benzene solution of triethylamine (1.2 g). The contents were refluxed in N_2 atmosphere for 4–6 h. Triethylamine hydrochloride (1.38 g, 1.47 calcd.) formed was filtered off and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The product triethyltin(IV) diethyl phosphite (1.83 g, 50 %) was obtained on distillation under reduced pressure (97 – $98^\circ/0.25$ mm) (Found : 34.44. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{P}$: Sn: 34.64%) (Table 1).

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